

Enablers Of Employee Performance Among The Education Faculty Of Balochistan, Pakistan: A Path Analysis

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Abstract

Presently, organizations confront significant challenges to enhance their employee performance (EP). The present study explores the EP through employee participation (EEP), employee relations (ER) and job involvement (JI) among the faculty members of the different education faculty of Balochistan, Pakistan. The study is employed a quantitative approach based on cross-sectional data. The survey questionnaire is applied as main source for data collection. The overall reliability of the instruments is found to be satisfactory. By employing the SEM through AMOS, path analysis underlines a positive and significant impact of EEP, ER and JI on EP. The study's outcomes would offer the advices and strategies to the policymakers and university authorities to increase the EP by improving employees' involvement, participation and developing good relations between employees and organizations. Finally, the empirical glimpses of the study would also enrich the depth of the related literature, particularly for developing contexts.

Introduction

In the present phase, the management of the EP has become a substantial task for every organization, more specifically in developing countries. EP is regarded as motivation and ability that employees frequently enjoy bringing the best (Moorhead & Griffin, 1998). It is about the tasks and the activities accomplished by an employee proficiently and efficiently (Saleem & Amin, 2013). To enhance EP, leaders apply financial and non-financial rewards as practical tools to inspire employees. Several scholars contend that equality and financial rewards are the foremost constructs that improve EP (Lavelle et al., 2010; Panagiotakopoulos, 2013). EP is established through multipurpose capacities, i.e., organizational, technological, and human levels. The starting point of the process of EP comes from top-line management.

Nonetheless, upshots are attained from bottom-line employees. Academicians and professionals demonstrate that performance always comes through methods and ways organizations adopted to accomplish their employees (Delaney, 1996). It can enhance business outcomes by assuming extraordinary measures, which comprise appraisal and reward schemes, job redesign, empowerment, skill-based training, job involvement and development programs (Pfeffer, 1998). According to Hartog et al. (2004), combining performance management methods with HRM practices can improve organizational performance (OP). EP leads to recover overall organizational efficiency and production process. Several factors are pointed in the literature that significantly affects the EP. These include training programs, administrative support, training content, supervisor support, monetary benefits, capacity developing programs etc. (Mwita, 2000; Abbas & Yaqoob, 2009; Bhatti et al., 2021a). Hargreaves (2011) and Gull et al. (2012) propose that EP is responsible for enhancing organizational profitability and production. However, in the banking sector of Pakistan, gender and JI significantly improve the EP (Hussain et al., 2012).

Consequently, the domain scholars applied numerous factors to investigate the EP among the different sectors, including banking, nursing and SMEs (Hussain et al., 2012; Soomro and Shah, 2019; Bhatti et al., 2021b) in Pakistan. However, the investigation of performance of education faculty is needs severe concentration. Therefore, the present study examines the predictors, i.e., EEP, ER, and JI, towards EP among the education faculty members of Balochistan, Pakistan. The study's findings would offer the plans to policymakers, planners and top management for enhancing the performance.

Literature review, model, and hypotheses development

Performance has become a significant challenge almost for all organizations. Consequently, organization performance (OP) is the foremost challenge (Armstrong & Baron, 1998). The OP depends on EP. For instance,

better EP higher than the OP. According to literature (Mwita, 2000; Abbas and Yaqoob, 2009), EP and OP make the tremendous productivity and the growth of the organizations (Armstrong & Baron, 1998). However, existing literature (Park, 2015) perceived that organizational support play a mediating role in developing the relationships between organizational commitment and EEP. To examine the predictors of EP at the workplace, a study conducted by Ahmad et al. (2015) among middle-level employees. The results of a study demonstrate a significant enhancement of EP through capacity building. Among the Bangladeshi employees, non-financial performance, i.e., sense of fulfillment and job autonomy are positively associated with employees' working life. Besides, the study underlines that a lack of skills is the EP's major challenge (Razzak et al., 2021). Soomro and Shah (2020) highlight that entrepreneurial orientation (EO) has no relationship with financial performance (FP), while strategic entrepreneurship develops the association between EO and FP. Ahmed et al. (2021) propose that task-oriented behaviour among leaders significantly fosters performance in the same domain. Further, the employees who perform better are regarded as in-group members by their leaders. According to Jena (2021), EP is predicted through workplace spirituality. Besides, organizational behaviour is a factor that also significantly contributes towards EP and workplace spirituality. EP can be boosted through employee's emotional intelligence. Similarly, the factors, i.e., organizational culture, autonomy, trust, dedication, vigor, absorption, enhance contextual performance (Bhardwaj & Kalia, 2021). An empirical investigation by Sarwar and Muhammad (2021) emphasizes that injustice perceptions create perceived incivility. On the other hand, perceived incivility, and organizational dehumanization significantly reduce the EP. The perceived incivility can develop the relationship between EP and interactional injustice. Both EEP and job performance can be forecasted by union commitment. Besides, EEP works as a mediator between job performance (JP) and union commitment. However, union commitment can be strengthened by affective commitment (Huang et al., 2020). Among the nursing context of Pakistan, Bhatti et al. (2021c) found a significant impact of learning styles and training context on EP rather than the trainer. Diamantidis and Chatzoglou (2019) claim that management support and job environment are the vital factors that enhance EP. On the other hand, motivation (intrinsic) and adaptability directly influence the JP. In SMEs of Pakistan, EP can be enhanced through job satisfaction, organizational culture and commitment. On the contrary, an EO has non-significant effect on EP (Soomro & Shah, 2019). By Applying, the SEM, Soomro et al. (2021) found a significant effect of organizational innovation and learning on EP among the CEOs of Pakistan. As a result, the different scholars provide the multidirectional factor responsible for enhancing EP in the various organizations (Diamantidis and Chatzoglou, 2019; Razzak et al., 2021; Bhatti et al., 2021c; Soomro et al., 2021). However, among faculty members of education faculty of Balochistan, Pakistan, EP needs to be explored through EEP, ER and JI. Thus, we planned the following model (Figure 1) for investigation among faculty members.

Figure 1. Conceptual model of the study

Employee participation (EEP) and employee performance (EP)

Workers' participation in decision making has a significant role in businesses as it influences maintaining competitiveness and quality. Involvement in the industry helps firms in developing and formulating activation mechanisms (Asokk et al., 2021). The reputation of employees is most useful and like an indispensable source to bring the competitive advantage in the firms, and ultimately it leads to the excellence of organizations. The employees get their resources to businesses they participate in by collaborating rather than as independent suppliers. In this manner, the workforce can make more value for the organization (Mayo, 2000). According to Oikonomou (2018), EEP significantly enhances teamwork performance. It also provides a road map to strengthen entrepreneurship. Similarly, it suggests that subordinates and managers alike participate in organizational affairs, i.e., information sharing, decision-making, and problem-solving, by undertaking participative management initiatives. A seminal work of Beardwell and Claydon, (2007) highlighted that EEP

unveils the partition and use of the power of both the managers, owners and the individuals working in the firms. Such the aspect underpins all the direct and indirect EEP related to the political and socio-technological organizational structures in the decision-making practice. In this sense, indirect involvement is related to decision-making that broadly links representatives employed in organizational structure.

Likewise, Luthans (2005) underlines that EEP emotionally, physically, and intellectually is associated with all types of decisions, i.e., formal and informal of the organizations. While, in the study of Graham and Bennet (1998), workers would have to provide all adequate information for discussion and compromise for any decision made and performed. In this way, the notion of EEP, in the present era, is a substance of profound interest for the mainstream of the employers as it perhaps consequences in increasing EP, refining their morality, and ultimately leading to higher job gratification. The researchers like (Miles & Snow, 1984; Damanpour, 1991) suggest that EEP practices are the HR schemes developed to stimulate employees and use their human capital through rational decision-making and financial opportunities. Such practices appear to fit with an innovative organizational climate. Likewise, the empirical outcomes of the study of Prasetyo et al. (2021) suggest that JI has a meaningful effect on work engagement. On the other hand, JI has no association with EP. Consequently, the relevant literature offers a significant association between EEP and EP in different contexts. To confirm these relationships among education faculty, we proposed:

H1. EEP positively and significantly predicts EP.

Employee relations (ER) and employee performance (EP)

ER is associated with generating and empowering a work environment for an excellent personal association in the organization. This gears towards the active elevation of the organizational objectives and goals. According to Nikoloski et al. (2014), ER underlines the correlation between employers and employees. Fundamentally, effective ER places a high quality on the human division in the organization, which promotes higher motivation, engagement and also improves productivity. A study by Yongcai (2010) highlights ER in organizations as the HRM field's particular characteristic. Similarly, Hassan et al. (2014) posit that a good ER is the outcome of adaptation of a suitable mechanism to adjust association amongst employees to fulfil the organizational tasks. In the perception of Pareek and Rai (2012), effective ER management in an organization improves the trust, loyalty and confidence amongst employees.

To get higher performance and lower absenteeism, the development of good ER is the best solution for the organizations (Padilla-Velez, 1993). Ahmed and Rafiq (2003) propose that ER has a significant effect on the entire company's success. Thus, the formation and settlement of internal ER are substantial for the industry's profitable operations and improve the EP. According to Al-Damoe (2015), ER supports undertaking and managing conflict at the workplace. They help their employers to be capable of identifying and avoiding conflicts ahead of time. Besides, it generates a culture that reflects the employees' interests and wellbeing. Similarly, in the hospitality industry of Pakistan, the empirical evidence of Chaudhry et al. (2013) suggests that ER practices are significantly and positively predict the EP. Brhane and Zewdie (2018) claim the positive relationship between organizational performance and ER among managers. However, Osborne and Hammoud (2017) concisely added that their contribution as a lower employee engagement creates a hostile work environment. According to Asamani (2015) positive human relations between the employees and employers are vital sources in improving EP in an organization. Likewise, human relations need concentration on what level employees are involved with their work (Shaheen et al., 2017). Moreover, in Tanzania, the findings of Samwel (2018) study underline a meaningful and robust relationship between ER and EP. As a result, several investigations have predicted positive and significant associations between ER and EP in a different context (Shaheen et al., 2017; Samwel, 2018; Asokk et al., 2021). However, among the education faculty members of Balochistan, these relationships are needed to be confirmed. Henceforth:

H2. ER positively and significantly predicts EP.

Job involvement (JI) and employee performance (EP)

JI indicates the extent of an employee's psychological association with individuals' employment (Kanungo, 1982). It highlights a perceptive attachment and their apprehensions about the job (Paullay et al., 1994). According to Lawler et al. (1992), JI includes the sense of governing one's work, accomplishing performance feedback and overall upright organizational performance. Employees, upon getting profits from the business and attempt to respond to it with EP. EI solves many concerns of the organizations, i.e., lower turnover, meaningful performance, job satisfaction and low absenteeism (Brown, 1996). Broadly, the involvement of employees is the core factor that enhances the productivity of an organization (Pfeffer, 1994; Soong, 2000). In the same domain, the empirical investigation of Rizwan et al. (2011) claims a significant and positive association between JI and EP. In the Macedonian manufacturing industry, the involvement of employees enhances the growth,

competitiveness, and performance in both regional and global markets (Sofijanov & Zabijakin-Chatleska, 2013). Likewise, the factors such as employees' commitment and JI enhance the production of the organizations (Mazayed et al., 2014). In a similar aspect, in Pakistan, a quantitative study by Danish et al. (2015) confirms the positive association between JI and organizational performance. On the other hand, more recently, Prasetyo et al. (2021) did not find any positive and significant connection between JI and EP. Therefore, the literature provides mixed relationships (positive and negative) (Soong, 2000; Sofijanov & Zabijakin-Chatleska, 2013; Danish et al., 2015; Prasetyo et al., 2021). Thus, to confirm the contradictory results, we developed:

H3. JI positively and significantly predicts EP.

Methods

Approach and data

We employed a quantitative approach. We followed the domain researchers who applied the same technique to assess the EP in the different contexts. We collected cross-sectional data. We used a random sampling technique to give an equal chance to the study participants. The higher educational institutes are significant sources for human resources development (Mohamad & Jais, 2016). Therefore, to acknowledge their EP is the need of the day. The context of the study was the faculty members who are working in the different education faculties in Balochistan, Pakistan.

Survey tools, procedure and sample size

The study employed a survey questionnaire. The items of the questionnaire are adapted from the concerned literature. All the items were assessed through a five-point Likert scale. We ranked the choices of scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Before handing over the questionnaires to the respondents, we formally consented to their voluntary participation in the study. We also ensured the privacy and confidentiality of their responses. In total, we distributed 300 surveys through personal visits and emails also. In return, we collected 171 raw samples with a response rate of 57%. Lastly, we applied 70 valid cases to infer the results.

Reliability and validity

Before collecting the large scale data, we ensured the reliability and validity of the questionnaire through a pilot study. We gauged the internal consistency among the items through factor loading and Cronbach's alpha (α). As a result, the loading scores and alpha are greater than 0.70, which are regarded as excellent scores. Besides, we ensured the validity of the questionnaire through field experts. The experts also suggest some modifications in terms of themes and language errors. Further, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy score is 0.725, which is more than average (Kaiser, 1974). Also, we rejected the null hypothesis through Bartlett's test of Sphericity that p-value is <0.0001 significant level with overall highly substantial validation.

Data analysis and results

We observed the descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation. We noted maximum mean scores (3.823) for the JI factor, while we noted ER factor with minimum mean scores (3.119) (Table 1). Similarly, we found a maximum standard deviation for EP (1.124) (Table 1). Besides, we applied Cronbach's alpha (α) reliability to gauge the internal consistency among the scale items. As a result, the questionnaire's overall reliability is found to be 0.887. The reliability of every factor is noted within the excellent ranges between 0.790 and 0.883 (Table 1). Henceforth, a reliable questionnaire was launched to get the large scale data.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics and reliability

S. No	Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation	α
1	EEP	3.234	0.900	0.883
2	ER	3.119	0.832	0.790
3	JI	3.823	1.092	0.862
4	EP	3.272	1.124	0.852

Note: EEP=employee participation; ER=employee relations; JI=job involvement; EP=employee performance; α = alpha reliability

In addition, we calculated Pearson correlation to measure the strength of the 'r' between the relationships among the variables (dependent and independent). In the Pearson correlation, the significant values with *and ** show the existence of the relationship or correlation (Cohen, 1988). In our study, we found a meaningful relationship

among all the variables (Table 2). A maximum correlation is found between EP and ER (0.470**). However, a minimum correlation has existed between EP JI and ER (0.244) (Table 2). In a simple sense, it can conclude that all the variables are significantly correlated with each other within acceptable values rather than multicollinearity.

Table 2. Person's correlation

Variables	EEP	ER	JI	EP
EEP	---			
ER	0.388**	---		
JI	0.419**	0.244*	---	
EP	0.354**	0.470**	0.249*	---

**, *Correlations are significant at 0.01 and 0.05 levels, respectively (two-tailed)

EEP=employee participation; ER=employee relations; JI=job involvement;

EP=employee performance

Before moving to the hypotheses assessment, we ensured the model fitness of the model. Consequently, we found the values of the CMIN= χ^2 /chi-square (2.231) within acceptable ranges. Besides, other model fit indices, i.e., GFI=0.902; NFI=; 0.909; CFI=0.933; and RMSEA= 0.027 were also noted within the acceptable ranges (Figure 2).

For hypotheses assessment, the path analysis shows a significant and positive impact of EEP on EP (SE=0.041, CR=5.339***; $p < 0.01$) (Figure 2 and Table 3). Henceforth, H1 is accepted. Further, the SEM scores also supported a predictive power of ER on EP (SE=0.067, CR=6.001***; $p < 0.01$) (Figure 2 and Table 3). Consequently, H2 is supported by the data. Finally, the results also confirmed a significant positive impact of JI on EP (SE=0.050, CR=6.524***; $p < 0.01$) (Figure 2 and Table 3). As a result, H3 also supported.

Figure 2. Path analysis

Note: EEP=employee participation; ER=employee relations; JI=job involvement; EP=employee performance

Table 2. Person's correlation

H.No.	Independent Variables	Path	Dependent Variables	Estimate	SE	CR	P	Decision
H1	EEP	→	EP	0.233	0.041	5.339	***	Accepted
H2	ER	→	EP	0.211	0.067	6.001	***	Accepted
H3	JI	→	EP	0.332	0.050	6.524	***	Accepted

Note: SE=standard error; CR=critical ratio; p =significance level *** $p < 0.05$

EEP=employee participation; ER=employee relations; JI=job involvement; EP=employee performance

Discussion and conclusion

The present study purposed to investigate the effect of EEP, ER and JI on EP among the education faculty members of Balochistan, Pakistan. Based on the literature, the conceptual model was developed based on the independent and dependent variables. We applied a deductive method based on cross-sectional data. All the requirements of the questionnaire, i.e., reliability and validity assumptions, were ensured with great precision and confidence. With regard to hypotheses, the results confirmed a significant and positive impact of EEP on EP. These results are in line with several studies like (Moyo, 2020; Oikonomou, 2018; Asokk et al., 2021; Prasetyo et al., 2021), who confirmed the same impacts between the EEP and EP. These outcomes may unveil the partition and use of the power of working in the firms. Among the faculty members, EEP practices are significantly developed to inspire employees. The EEP covers and develops the attitudes of employees towards EP through the different programs and skills.

Concerning the second hypothesis, we confirmed ER's significant and positive effect on EP (H2 accepted). The findings also concur with several research studies, i.e., (Shaheen et al., 2017; Samwel, 2018; Asokk et al., 2021), who underlined a meaningful and healthy relationship between ER and EP. The findings may highlight that ER gears the faculty to get the EP through a high-quality human division in the organization, which endorses higher motivation, engagement and also improves productivity (Nikoloski et al., 2014). The positive association between ER and EP is the sign of adapting a suitable mechanism to regulate connotation amongst employees to fulfil the organizational responsibilities (Yongcai, 2010).

Finally, the positive association between JI and EP are supported by the findings (H3 accepted). These relationships are also supported by the various domain studies like (Soong, 2000; Sofijanov & Zabijakin-Chatleska, 2013; Danish et al., 2015), who provided evidence of the positive associations between them. On the other hand, these results are not supported by Prasetyo et al. (2021). The study's positive outcomes may underline that JI is the protagonist factor that improves productivity (Pfeffer, 1994; Soong, 2000). The faculty members think that through JI, the EP can enhance the university ranking appropriately.

In conclusion, overall results show a significant positive impact of EEP, ER and JI on EP among the education faculty members. The study's findings would provide the guidelines in developing the policies and plans that may enhance the EP. Besides, the study results would contribute to the literature of management, particularly for developing nations. The study has certain limitations. The base of the study is only on cross-sectional data. We only applied the quantitative approach to achieve the aim of the study. We did not use any concerned theory to underpin the conceptualization of the study.

References

- Abbas, Q., & Yaqoob, S. (2009). Effect of leadership development on employee performance in Pakistan. *Pakistan Economic and Social review*, 47(2), 269-292.
- Ahmad, T., Farrukh, F., & Nazir, S. (2015). Capacity building boost employees' performance. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 47(2), 61-66.
- Ahmed, I., Afzal, R., & Rasid, A. S.Z. (2021). Employees' task performance and propensity to take charge: the role of LMX and leader's task orientation. *Journal of Management Development*, 40(3), 224-239.
- Ahmed, P.K., & Rafiq, M. (2003). Internal marketing issues and challenges. *European Journal of Marketing*, 37(9), 1177-1186.
- Al-Damoe, F. M. (2015). Human resource management practices on organizational performance in Libya firm. *Asian Social Science*, 11(23), 51-58.
- Armstrong, M., & Baron, A. (1998). *Performance management: The new realities*. London: IPD.
- Asamani, L. (2015). Interpersonal trust at work and employers' organizational citizenship behavior. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 3(11), 17-29.
- Asokk, D., Gudda, A., Bhati, P., & Vanishree, C.T. (2021). The impact of employee involvement in decision making on an organisational performance. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 8(1), 1200-1212.
- Beardwell, J., & Claydon, J. (2007). *Human resource management: a contemporary approach*. 5th ed. Great Britain, Pearson Education Limited.
- Bhardwaj, B., & Kalia, N. (2021). Contextual and task performance: role of employee engagement and organizational culture in hospitality industry. *Vilakshan - XIMB Journal of Management*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/XJM-08-2020-0089>.
- Bhatti, M.K., Soomro, B.A., & Shah, N. (2021a). Predictive power of training design on employee performance: an empirical approach in Pakistan's health sector. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-09-2020-0489>.
- Bhatti, M.K., Soomro, B.A., & Shah, N. (2021b). Work environment and performance among nurses: a significant way to overcome violation of human rights in the health sector. *International Journal of Human Rights in Healthcare*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJHRH-03-2021-0064>.

- Bhatti, M.K., Soomro, B.A., & Shah, N. (2021c). Training characteristics and employees' performance among the nurses in Pakistan. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEAS-02-2021-0026>
- Brhane, H., & Zewdie, S. (2018). A literature review on the effects of employee relation on improving employee performance. *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, 6(4), 66-76.
- Brown, S.P. (1996). A meta-analysis and review of organizational research on job involvement. *Psychological Bulletin*, 120(2), 235-255.
- Chaudhry, M.S., Sohail, F., & Riaz, N. (2013). Impact of employee relation on employee performance in hospitality industry of Pakistan. *Entrepreneurship and Innovation Management Journal*, 1(1), 60-72.
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences*. 2nd ed. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Damanpour, F. (1991). Organizational innovation: a meta-analysis of effects of determinants and moderators. *Academy of Management Journal*, 34(3), 555-590.
- Danish, R.Q., Shahid, A.U., Aslam, N., Afzal, M., & Ali, H.Y. (2015). Relationship between JOB performance, JOB involvement and career salience of employees in education sector of Pakistan. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 1(2), 19-23.
- Delaney, T.J. (1996). The impact of human resource management practices on perceptions of organizational performance. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 39(4), 949-69.
- Diamantidis, A.D., & Chatzoglou, P. (2019). Factors affecting employee performance: an empirical approach. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 68(1), 171-193.
- Graham, H., & Bennet, R. (1998). *Human resource management*. 9th ed. Great Britain: Pearson Education Limited.
- Gull, A., Akbar, S., & Jan, Z. (2012). Role of capacity development, employee empowerment and promotion on employee retention in the banking sector of Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 2(9), 284-300.
- Hargreaves, T. (2001). Practicing behaviour change: applying social practice theory to pro-environmental behaviour change. *Journal of Consumer Culture*, 11(1), 79-99.
- Hartog, D., Boselie, P., & Paauwe, J. (2004). Performance management: a model and research agenda. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 53(4), 556-69.
- Hassan, J., Saeid, J., Hashim, F., Bin, Y., & Khalil, M. N. (2014). The impact of emotional intelligence on communication effectiveness: focus on strategic alignment. *African Journal of Marketing Management*, 6(6), 82-87.
- Huang, W., Yuan, C., Shen, J., & Li, M. (2020). Effects of union commitment on job performance in China. *Personnel Review*, 50(4), 1185-1199.
- Hussain, A., Sardar, S., Usman, M., & Ali, A. (2012). Factors affecting the job performance: in case of Pakistani banking sector. *Finance Management*, 47, 8726-30.
- Jena, L.K. (2021). Does workplace spirituality lead to raising employee performance? The role of citizenship behavior and emotional intelligence. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOA-06-2020-2279>.
- Kaiser, H.F. (1974). An index of factorial simplicity. *Psychometrika*, 39(1), 31-6.
- Kanungo, R. N. (1982). Measurement of job and work involvement. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 67(3), 341-349.
- Lavelle, J., Gunnigle, P., & McDonnell, A. (2010). Patterning employee voice in multinational companies. *Human Relations*, 63(3), 395-418.
- Lawler, E. E., Mohrman, S., & Ledford, G. (1992). *Employee involvement and total quality management: Practices and results in Fortune 100 companies*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass
- Luthans, F. (2005). *Organisational behavior*. 10th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Mazayed, K., Khan, M.S., Kundi, G.M., Qureshi, Q.A., Akhtar, R., & Bilal, H. (2014). Assessing the impact of job involvement and commitment on organizational productivity in the Arab/Gulf countries. *Industrial Engineering Letters*, 4(3), 18-22.
- Miles, R.E., & Snow, C.C. (1984). Designing strategic human resources systems. *Organizational Dynamics*, 13(1), 36-52
- Mohamad, M., & Jais, J. (2016). Emotional intelligence and job performance: a study among Malaysian teachers. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 35(2016), 674-682.
- Moorhead, G., & Griffin, R. (1989). *Organizational behavior*. 2nd ed. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company.
- Moyo, A. (2020). The role of employee development in the growth of intellectual capital. *Personnel Review*, 29(4), 521-533.
- Mwita, J. I. (2000). Performance management model: a system-based approach to system quality. *The International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 13(1), 19-37.

- Nikoloski, K., Dimitrova, J., Koleva, B., & Kacarski, E. (2014). From industrial relations to employment relations with focus on employee relations. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research*, 18(2), 117-124.
- Oikonomou, A. (2018). Assessing the impact of employee participation on team-work performance: a way to reinforce entrepreneurship. *SPOUDAI - Journal of Economics and Business*, 68(2/3), 48-61.
- Osborne, S., & Hammoud, M. S. (2017). Effective employee engagement in the workplace. *International Journal of Applied Management and Technology*, 16(1), 50-67.
- Padilla-Velez, D. (1993). Job satisfaction of vocational teachers in Puerto Rico. The Ohio State University.
- Panagiotakopoulos, A. (2013). The impact of employee learning on staff motivation in Greek small firms: The employees' perspective. *Developing and Learning in Organization: An International Journal*, 27(2), 13-15.
- Pareek, V., & Rai, A. K. (2012). Building relationship with employees: an employee relationship management model. *Journal of the Management Training Institute*, 39(4), 32-37.
- Park, R. (2015). Employee participation and outcomes: organizational strategy does matter. *Employee Relations*, 37(5), 604-622.
- Paullay, I. M., Alliger, G. M., Stome, R., & Eugene, F. (1994). Construct validation of two instruments designed to measure job involvement and work centrality. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 79(2), 224-228.
- Pfeffer, J. (1994). *Competitive advantage through people*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press.
- Pfeffer, J. (1998). Seven practices of successful organizations. *California Management Review*, 40 (2), 96-124.
- Prasetyo, Kusmaningtyas, A., & Nugroho, R. (2021). Effect of job involvement on employee performance through work engagement at Bank Jatim. *Universal Journal of Management*, 9(2), 29-37.
- Razzak, B.M., Blackburn, R., & Saridakis, G. (2021). Employees' working life and performance of UK ethnic minority restaurants: a qualitative approach. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-08-2020-0436>.
- Rizwan, M., Khan, D.J., & Saboor, F. (2011). Relationship of job involvement with employee performance: moderating role of attitude. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 3(8), 77-85.
- Saleem, S., & Amin, S. (2013). The impact of organizational support for career development and supervisory support on employee performance: an empirical study from Pakistani academic sector. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(5), 194-207.
- Samwel, J.O. (2018). Effect of employee relations on employee performance and organizational performance-study of small organizations in Tanzania. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 18(8), 68-79.
- Sarwar, A., & Muhammad, L. (2021). Impact of organizational mistreatment on employee performance in the hotel industry. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 33(2), 513-533.
- Shaheen, A., Fais Bin, A., & Abdul, R. J. (2017). Employee engagement on employee relations with supervisor and employee performance relationship in developing economy: Critical analysis with PLS-SEM. *Saudi Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 2(4A), 389- 398.
- Sofijanova, E., & Zabijakin-Chatleska, V. (2013). Employee involvement and organizational performance: evidence from the manufacturing sector in republic of Macedonia. *Trakia Journal of Sciences*, 11(1), 31-36.
- Soomro, B.A., & Shah, N. (2020). Entrepreneurial orientation and performance in a developing country: Strategic entrepreneurship as a mediator. *Business Strategy and Development*, 3(4), 567-577.
- Soomro, B.A., & Shah, N. (2019). Determining the impact of entrepreneurial orientation and organizational culture on job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and employee's performance. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 8(3), 266-282.
- Soomro, B.A., Mangi, S., & Shah, N. (2021). Strategic factors and significance of organizational innovation and organizational learning in organizational performance. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 24(2), 481-506.
- Soong, S. W. (2000). *The study on the devotion and job satisfaction of adults' participation in volunteer services*. Taiwan: National Kaohsiung Normal University.
- Yongcai, Y. (2010). Employee relationship management of small and medium-sized enterprises. 2010 International Conference on E-Business and E-Government, 940-943.

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